

POLY(ETHYLENE 2,6-NAPHTHALATE) - PEN AS THERMOPLASTIC MATRIX FOR HIGH PERFORMANCE WOVEN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this work, we investigate the use of PEN as matrix for composite laminates with the aim to develop fibre reinforced structures with service temperature of at least 100°C. Three different typologies of fibres were considered as reinforcement in woven fabric form: carbon type, polymeric (aramid and Vectran) and mineral (basalt). Composites were manufactured by using the film stacking technique, alternating layers of balanced plain weave fabrics (0°/90°) and films of amorphous PEN, keeping the fibre volume fraction around 40%. The compression moulding process was optimized to obtain a good fabric impregnation and to keep the void content very low.

The structural response of the prepared composites was evaluated by means of static flexural tests and dynamic mechanical scans up to 220 °C, in both cases by using the 3-point bending geometry. A falling dart testing machine was also used to evaluate the effect of the fibre type on the impact resistance of composites. The flexural modulus and strength of laminates resulted to be very high and the storage modulus from DMA scans indicated a service temperature of up to 100 °C. The impact resistance of the composites was dependent on the fibres type. These results proved that PEN is a very interesting matrix for the production of structural composites with a high performance/cost ratio.

1 INTRODUCTION

Reinforced thermoplastic composites offer to the aerospace industry as well as to other high demanding industries the opportunity to couple the structural performances with weight and cost savings and with a more environmental oriented technology with respect to thermosets [1]. Thermoplastic polymers have increased impact resistance, higher damage tolerance and interlaminar toughness due to the presence of the amorphous phase that can retard the crack propagation and allow larger deformations [2].

Among the thermoplastic polymers, poly(ethylene 2,6-naphthalate) is a good candidate for the production of high performance/cost ratio composites with high service temperature when compared to semicrystalline polymers like PPS and PEEK. In fact, it has a glass transition temperature higher than 120°C and a melting temperature of around 265°C, which reduces the power requirements for its processing. PEN has a very good thermal stability, very low moisture absorption and it can withstand to a wide range of solvents. Despite those advantages, a limited literature is available on the use of such polymer in composite applications [3].

In this work, we study the employability of PEN as a matrix for composites laminates with the aim to develop systems with high mechanical performance up to 100°C. In order to exploit the potential of PEN, woven fabrics based on different reinforcing fibres were used and the static, dynamic and impact properties were compared.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Raw materials

The thermoplastic matrix used for the laminate preparation is the Poly(ethylene 2,6-naphthalate) homopolymer (PEN) (Teonex TN8065S from Teijin Kasei, Japan). According to the manufacturer, this polymer has a density of 1.35 g/cm³ (25°C), glass transition temperature of 120°C and melting temperature of 265°C. Amorphous PEN presents maximum flexural strain of 4.94±0.01%, flexural modulus of 2.20±0.09 GPa and maximum flexural strength 93.4±0.8 MPa, all evaluated with three point flexural tests [3].

The carbon fibre woven fabric reinforcement was supplied by SAATI S.p.a., Italy (model CC160P). It is a plain weave fabric with surface weight of 160 g/m² and yarn count of 4.0 ends/cm (warp and weft). According to the supplier data-sheet, the carbon fibres employed are high strength carbon fibre 3K 2000 dtex. Those fibres are characterized by a density of 1.76 g/cm³, an average diameter of 7 µm, Young's modulus of 235±5 GPa, and tensile strength of 4.1±0.3 GPa.

The basalt fibre reinforcement (BAS 220.1270.P) was supplied by Basaltex-Flocart NV, Belgium. It is a plain weave fabric with surface weight of 220 g/m², yarn count of 7.2 ends/cm (warp and weft) and nominal thickness of 0.13 mm. According to the supplier data-sheet, the basalt fibres employed (KVT150tex13-I) have a density of 2.67 g/cm³, an average diameter of 13±1.5 µm, Young's modulus of 85±2 GPa and melting point of 1350±100 °C.

Woven fabrics reinforcements based on aramidic and Vectran fibres were supplied by G.Angeloni srl, Italy. The aramidic reinforcement (KK220P) is a plain weave fabric with surface weight of 224 g/m² and yarn count of 6.5 ends/cm (warp and weft). According to the supplier data-sheet, the aramidic fibres employed are standard Twaron 2200 (1620 dtex). Those fibres have a density of 1.45 g/cm³, Young's modulus of 70±10 GPa and melting point of 500 °C. The Vectran reinforcement (VcT200T) is a 2x2 twill weave fabric with surface weight of 201 g/m² and yarn count of 6.0 ends/cm (warp and weft). The Vectran HT fibres have a density of 1.4 g/cm³, an average diameter of 23 µm, Young's modulus of 75±7 GPa, tensile strength of 3.2 GPa and maximum service temperature of 450°C.

2.2 Composite manufacturing

Thin films of PEN were prepared from pellets pressed at 300 °C and 50 bars for 5 minutes, by using the compression moulding technique. Films with a mean thickness of 150 µm were produced and quenched to keep the polymer in the amorphous state. All materials (PEN pellets, films and reinforcing fabrics) were dried in oven by applying vacuum at 120°C for at least 6h.

Composite plates were prepared by using the film stacking process. Layers of the reinforcing fabric are alternatively stacked (with a 0°/90° orientation of fabric threads) between layers of PEN films in a mold with fixed (dimensions of 160 mm x 160 mm as length and width) and then pressed by using a hydraulic hot plate press (model P 300P, Collin GmbH, Germany). Temperature and pressure profiles were optimized to obtain a very good impregnation of fibres. The processing sequence consists of a heating step at 300 °C and 0 N/cm² for two minutes in order to melt the PEN film, followed by a compression step at 300 °C and 25.35 N/cm² for five minutes to force the fabric's impregnation. At the end of the compression step, the mold with the composite plate is quickly cooled thus hindering the formation of crystals in the polymer to obtain an almost amorphous matrix in the composite. The need for keeping PEN in the amorphous state is due to the fact that the presence of crystals (ordered packing of a fraction of the thermoplastic macromolecules) increases the local density of the polymer and induces residual stresses that can generate microcracks in the laminate during the used cooling process. Those laminates presented very low void content and good fabric

impregnation, as confirmed by the morphological analysis performed with the SEM and reported elsewhere [3].

In Table 1, the main characteristics of each laminate configuration (mean values and variance of fibre volume content, density and thickness) are reported. Due to the different surface weights of fabrics, some laminate configurations showed a lower thickness. In particular, carbon and basalt based reinforcements showed a significantly lower thickness with respect to aramid and Vectran based laminates. Since the composite thickness has a strong influence on impact properties [4–6], further composite plates based on carbon and basalt fabrics were produced with a higher number of fabric layers in order to have a homogeneous thickness among all tested systems (Table 1).

Composite plate	fibre volume ratio	Number of plies	Density [g/cm ³]	Thickness [mm]
PEN/Carbon _{8L}	40±1%	8	1.51±0.01	1.73±0.04
PEN/Basalt _{8L}	39±2%	8	1.87±0.03	1.70±0.05
PEN/Aramid _{8L}	41±1%	8	1.39±0.02	2.82±0.09
PEN/Vectran _{8L}	40±1%	8	1.37±0.02	2.73±0.06
PEN/Carbon _{12L}	41±1%	12	1.52±0.01	2.60±0.08
PEN/Basalt _{14L}	40±1%	14	1.88±0.01	2.72±0.05

Table 1 List of plates of PEN composites manufactured.

2.3 Characterization procedures

Static three point bending tests were performed according to the ASTM D790 standard, by means of a universal testing machine (model 4304 from SANS – China, now MTS – USA) equipped with a 30 kN load cell. The loading nose and supports of the three point bending fixture are made of stainless steel and have cylindrical surfaces with radius of curvature equal to 5 mm. Five samples for each laminate configuration, having dimensions of 100 mm x 12.7 mm (length x width) were tested. The span-to-depth ratio used is 32 to 1. The strain rate of the outer fibres during the laminates testing was equal to 0.01 mm/mm/min. Load-deflection curves were plotted to determine average values and standard deviation of flexural strength (σ_y) and flexural modulus of elasticity (E_B).

Thermo-dynamic mechanical properties of both matrix and composites were evaluated with a dynamic mechanical analyzer (TRITEC 2000 DMA, from Triton Technology, UK) by following the ASTM D 5023 Standard. DMA tests were performed with a three-point bending configuration (dynamic displacement amplitude of 50 mm, frequency of 1 Hz) in a temperature range from room temperature to 220 °C (or until the occurrence of failure) and using a heating rate of 2 °C/min. Neat PEN specimens were cut with dimensions of 32 mm x 10 mm x 1.0 mm and a support span of 20 mm was used (span-to-depth ratio of 20:1). Composite specimens were cut with dimensions of 43 mm x 12 mm x 1.6 mm with a support span of 25 mm (span-to-depth ratio of 16:1).

Impact tests were performed by using a falling dart impact testing machine, model Fractovis Plus from CEAST (Pianezza - TO, Italy) with a hemispherical impact head (diameter equal to 12.7 mm). Specimens had dimensions of 60 mm x 60 mm and were clamped on a circular support with inner diameter of 40 mm and outer diameter of 60 mm.

Several impact energies were applied to each typology of composite plate to determinate the respective perforation impact energy. The impact energies varied from 1.1J to 60J. For impact energies higher than 3J, the impactor mass was kept constant at 4.93 Kg and the velocity was changed in order to reach the desired impact energy. For impact energies between 1.1 and 3J the impactor mass was reduced to 1.93 Kg. For all tests, impact velocity varied from 1.06 m/s to 4.92 m/s.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Three-point bending test

Representative stress/strain curves for each typology of composite tested are presented in Figure 1. Those curves have been selected for specimens of each typology in order to show a curve that can

represent at best the average behaviour among the 5 tested specimens. A clear difference of static mechanical behaviour for each PEN configuration can be detected, depending on the type of reinforcing fibre.

The average values and standard deviations of the measured mechanical parameters (flexural modulus, flexural strength and strain at yield) from static flexural tests of composites with 8 fabric layers are summarized in Table 2.

<i>Composite plate</i>	E_B [GPa]	σ_y [MPa]	ϵ_y [%]
PEN/Carbon	38.8±0.9	714±53	2.0±0.1
PEN/Basalt	19.8±1.5	365±41	2.7±0.6
PEN/Aramid	17.2±0.7	224±24	2.9±0.4
PEN/Vectran	11.4±0.4	> 190	> 5.0

Table 2 Mean values and standard deviations of the flexural modulus (E_B), the flexural strength (σ_y) and the strain at yield (ϵ_y).

PEN/Carbon composites, as expected, are the most stiff and have an almost completely elastic brittle behaviour. PEN/Basalt composites follow, also presenting a brittle behaviour with limited plasticity. PEN/Aramid composites presented an initial stiffness similar to that of PEN/Basalt composites but then they turned to a more plastic behaviour, showing a plastic plateau and reaching higher strains with lower ultimate strength. PEN/Vectran composites presented the lowest stiffness among all composites, but reached the limit of strain deformation (specified by the applied standard (ASTM D790) as 5%) with almost no sign of damage. PEN/Vectran composites were also tested with a strain rate (calculated for the outer fibres) equal to 0.10 mm/mm/min (10 times faster than the previous test), as indicated by the standard in cases no rupture happens within the 5 % limit strain. Also at this strain rate the mechanical behaviour was almost the same, and no evidences of fibre breakage was detected. Further tests in tensile mode should be performed to get more information about the strain and stress limits of PEN/Vectran composite configuration. In fact, it has been reported that Vectran fibres on tensile test present ultimate strength of 63 MPa and maximum strain of around 6% [7].

Figure 1 Stress/strain curves from flexural tests on PEN composites.

3.2 Dynamic mechanical tests

DMA tests are considered to correctly represent the influence of temperature on the elastic behaviour of a material, but the absolute value of the elastic modulus measured by this technique usually differs from that measured by static mechanical tests, although in principle they should be very similar. This discrepancy has been discussed by Deng et al [8] who concluded that the use of the three point bending configuration for the DMA testing can give results very close to those from static testing. Besides machine and test parameters, discrepancies in the absolute value of elastic modulus could also be related to specimen characteristics such as reinforcement orientation, dispersion on mechanical and physical properties, matrix impregnation, porosity and geometry dimensions. To compensate these issues, in the present study DMA tests were performed on four specimens for each system (unreinforced PEN and PEN composites) and the mean curves of storage modulus versus temperature were calculated. In Figure 2, the mean curves of storage modulus versus temperature are presented for PEN/Carbon, PEN/Basalt and neat amorphous PEN. Their shapes confirm an almost linear dependence of the storage modulus on the temperature in the investigated temperature range, and a good retention of the stiffness for these materials up to the glass transition temperature of the polymer (higher than 100 °C). The slopes of the initial part of the curves for neat PEN polymer and PEN composites are pretty similar, a fact that support the statement that the decrease of the composite flexural behaviour with temperature is dominated by the thermoplastic matrix behaviour. On the contrary, the stiffness (absolute values of the storage modulus) is mostly dependent on the reinforcement properties.

Figure 2 Mean curves of storage modulus versus temperature are presented for PEN/Carbon, PEN/Basalt and neat amorphous PEN.

3.3 Impact tests

The perforation energies were determined for all typologies of PEN composite under investigation. The perforation energy is the impact energy needed to completely perforate the material and is measured from impacted tests as the absorbed energy after the perforation occurs [9]. The Figure 1 presents the absorbed energies for each typology of PEN composite tested as a function of the impact energy. This comparison shows that the absorbed energy increases with the impact energy until a plateau is reached, at which the absorbed energy becomes almost constant. The plateau value of the absorbed energy represents the material perforation energy and the mean values and standard deviation by composite typology are reported in Table 3 together with the number of reinforcing layers and the composite thickness. Figure 3 shows that the perforation energy has good repeatability on those tests

and it was not dependent on impact velocity. PEN/Basalt_{14L} and PEN/Aramid_{8L} were the laminates with the highest perforation energies, while PEN/Carbon_{12L} showed the lowest performance. PEN/Basalt_{8L} composite presented a perforation energy about three times higher than that for the PEN/Carbon_{8L} composite (24 J to 8.7 J, respectively). Among the 8 layer thick composite samples, PEN/Aramid_{8L} presented a perforation energy of about 38.2 J, while the PEN/Vectran_{8L} of 29.4 J.

Thicker PEN/Basalt_{14L} and PEN/Carbon_{12L} composites also presented a ratio between their perforation energies of about 3 (44.3 J to 15.3 J, respectively). Comparing them to composites with similar thickness (namely PEN/Aramid_{8L} PEN/Vectran_{8L}) PEN/Basalt_{14L} composite showed the highest impact perforation energy while the PEN/Carbon_{12L} still showed the lowest value. Those results indicate that, at constant fibre volume ratio and composite thickness, the PEN/Basalt system has the highest impact resistance, followed by PEN/Aramid, PEN/Vectran, while the PEN/Carbon system always has the lowest impact resistance.

Figure 3 Absorbed energy as a function of impact energy for each typology of PEN composite studied.

Composite plate	Number of layers	Thickness [mm]	Perforation energy [J]
PEN/Carbon _{8L}	8	1.73±0.04	8.7±0.3
PEN/Basalt _{8L}	8	1.70±0.05	24.0±0.5
PEN/Aramid _{8L}	8	2.82±0.09	38.2±0.9
PEN/Vectran _{8L}	8	2.73±0.06	29.4±0.2
PEN/Carbon _{12L}	12	2.60±0.08	15.3±0.2
PEN/Basalt _{14L}	14	2.72±0.05	44.3±0.2

Table 3 Values of perforation energy measured for each typology of PEN composite studied.

The difficulty in comparing the penetration energy data for composite materials comes from the fact that many factors, either from an internal or external source, can affect the impact response of the laminate, and in particular its energy absorbing capability. Caprino and Lopresto [6] studied this issue, analyzing data published in several scientific works and concluded that the main factors affecting the penetration energy of the material are the total fibre thickness ($t \times V_f$) and the impactor diameter (D_i). They showed that parameters as the resin type and content, reinforcement architecture, laminate stacking sequence, and fibre orientations play a secondary role in determining the energy absorption capacity. Based on their findings, they proposed that the parameter actually influencing the penetration

energy is the product of total fibre thickness times the impactor diameter ($t \times V_f \times D_t$) and that the relationship correlating the penetration energy to ($t \times V_f \times D_t$) is a power law:

$$U_{perf} = K * (t * V_f * D_t)^\alpha \quad (1)$$

where K and α are two parameters, related to the specific material, to be experimentally determined.

This yields a powerful tool to compare impact results obtained under different impact conditions and from different studies. Figure 4 plots the perforation energies (U_{perf}) as function of ($t \times V_f \times D_t$) for the different laminates. The fitting curves from Eq. 1 were determined for the PEN/Basalt and PEN/Carbon composites. Curves related to carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP) and glass-fibre reinforced polymers (GRP), taken from Caprino and Lopresto [6], were also plotted for comparison. In this figure, it is evident the superiority of the PEN/Basalt composite in terms of impact energy needed to perforate the material, when compared to the other tested systems (PEN/Aramid, PEN/Vectran and PEN/Carbon). Comparing to data from literature, it also indicates that Basalt, Vectran and Aramid fabrics were able to impart to composites superior performances in comparison to both glass based (GRP) and carbon based (CFRP and PEN/Carbon) systems.

Figure 4 Perforation energy as a function of the quantity ($t \times V_f \times D_t$).

4 CONCLUSIONS

Thermoplastic composites based on PEN and high performance woven fabrics with a fibre volume content higher than around 40% were successfully prepared by using the film-stacking technique. A very good impregnation with very low void content was achieved. Composites were characterized under static and dynamic mechanical conditions. The flexural modulus and strength of laminates resulted to be very high. DMA tests showed that the developed composites show high storage moduli up to 100 °C. The impact resistance of composites was dependent on the fibres type. In particular, basalt fibre fabrics imparted the highest impact resistance among the tested reinforcement, followed by aramidic fibres. The analysis of data from static and impact characterizations indirectly evidenced a very good interface strength between PEN and all fibres. These results proved that PEN is a very promising matrix for the production of structural composites where a high performance/cost ratio is needed.

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